

DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN COUNTRY SPIRITS.

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A method has been worked out for the estimation of copper in country spirits by use of the reagent diethyl dithiocarbamate, which has been found useful specially in cases where the percentage of copper or the quantity of spirit submitted for test is very small.

Country spirits, *i.e.* potable spirits made from *gur*, molasses, mahua etc., with or without flavouring, are examined for contamination with metals such as copper, iron, lead or zinc which may be present as a result of using metallic plant and storage vessels in the distilleries. As copper stills and pipes are mostly used, contamination with this metal is commonly found both in plain and spiced liquors. A permissible maximum limit of one quarter grain per gallon of spirit has been prescribed for copper (*vide* C. H. Bedford, "Technical Excise Manual," p. 50).

The determination of copper is generally carried out by dissolving the ash from 20 ml. of spirit in a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and removing any iron present by ammonium hydroxide. After acidifying the ammoniacal filtrate with dilute acetic acid, a few drops of freshly prepared potassium ferrocyanide are added and the copper estimated by matching the intensity of the reddish brown colour produced against known standards.

This method is not satisfactory because (a) the colour produced in acid solution tends to change from a reddish to an earthy brown, and (b) reliable results cannot be obtained when the quantity of copper is less than 0.1 grain per gallon of spirit.

Several reagents were tested for the colorimetric estimation of copper, *e.g.*, dimethylglyoxime (Clark and Jones, *Analyst*, 1925, 54, 333), potassium iodide (Dunncliff and Ram, *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 168), pyridine and potassium thiocyanate (Spacu, *Bull. Soc. Stiinte Cluj*, 1922, 1, 352), sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (Callan and Henderson, *Analyst*, 1929, 54, 650), rubeanic acid (Allport and Skrimshire, *Quart. J. Pharmacol.*, 1932, 5, 461), salicylaldoxime (Astin and Riley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 314), and α -benzoin oxime Gruzewaka and Russel, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, 121, 289).

In the experience of the authors the potassium ferrocyanide method as described by Scott and Furman ("Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 5th Ed., Vol. 1, p. 377), slightly modified, is suitable when the concentration of copper exceeds 0.1 grain per gallon of spirit and the sodium

diethyldithiocarbamate method (*Analyst*, 1939, 64, 339) when the copper is in traces or when the quantity of spirit submitted for test is very small.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Preparation of the Sample.—To 20 ml. of the spirit under test in an evaporating dish, add 1 ml. of dilute sulphuric acid (10 per cent. w/w). Evaporate almost to dryness on a water-bath (heating gently in the beginning) and ignite the residue over a clear flame to eliminate the sulphuric acid. Cool, dissolve the residue in 2 ml. of distilled water, add 2-3 drops of aqua regia and evaporate to dryness on a water-bath. Dissolve the residue in distilled water (removing if necessary iron by double precipitation for the ferrocyanide method only) and make up the volume to 25 ml. Determine copper by either of the two methods detailed below depending upon the quantity of copper present.

The solutions are essentially the same as those given by Scott and Furnian (*loc. cit.*) except that the standard copper solutions are made up as follows:—

Solution A.—Dissolve 1·119 g. of A. R. copper sulphate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in distilled water and dilute to 1,000 ml. (1 ml. = 0·0002845 g. or 0·00439 grains of copper). This solution is retained as a stock solution.

Solution B.—It is made up immediately before use by taking 10 ml. of this solution and diluting to 100 ml. (1 ml. = 0·00002845 g. or 0·000439 grain copper).

Procedure.—Measure 0·25 ml. of freshly prepared 4 % ammonium nitrate solution into a Nessler tube of 50 ml. capacity and then add 25 ml. of the neutral solution of the assay prepared as directed above. Dilute to 50 ml. Simultaneously prepare in the same way four comparison tubes to which is added from a burette 1·0, 2·0, 2·5 and 3·0 ml. of standard solution B respectively. Make up the volume in each tube to 50 ml. Mix thoroughly and compare the colour with that of the assay by viewing the liquid from the top against a white surface (or use a colorimeter). The temperature of the solutions should be kept below 20°.

The number of ml. of standard solution B, required by the comparison tube, which matches with the colour of the solution of the sample under test, multiplied by 0·1, gives the weight of copper in grains per gallon in the sample of spirit.

Sodium Diethyldithiocarbamate Method.

The reagent gives a golden brown colour in acid, ammoniacal or neutral solutions and is used for the colorimetric determination of copper

when the spirit contains less than 0·1 grain of the metal per gallon of spirit.

Special Solutions : (i) Standard copper solution ; same as above.

(ii) A 0·1% solution of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate $(C_2H_5)_2N^{\cdot}CSSNa$ in distilled water. This reagent keeps well for several weeks in an amber-coloured bottle.

Procedure : (a) *Without Extraction*.—In a 50 ml. Nessler tube, take 10 ml. of the neutral solution of the assay from which iron has not been removed. Add 2 g. of citric and 10 c.c. of (10% v/v) ammonia, or more until $p_H = 9$. Make up to 50 ml. with distilled water.

Prepare a series of standard comparison solutions, each containing in 50 ml., 2 g. of citric acid, and ammonia solution of $p_H 9$ together with increasing amounts of copper (i.e., 0·1, 0·4, 0·6, 0·8 and 1·0 ml. of standard copper solution B).

The test solutions and standards should be water-white.

Cool all solutions to 20° and to each add 2 ml. of diethyldithiocarbamate and match the test solution against the standard comparison solutions.

(b) *Extraction Method*.—Extract immediately the copper organo-metallic compound produced as in (a), with four successive portions (2·5 ml. each) of carbon tetrachloride and compare the colour of the solution so obtained in a colorimeter with the extracts of standard solutions similarly prepared. Chloroform may be used but carbon tetrachloride is better as it is almost insoluble in water and forms clearer solutions which separate quickly.

The number of ml. of standard solution B used in the tube having the same shade as that of the sample, multiplied by 0·25 gives the weight of copper in grains per gallon of this sample.

A blank experiment must be carried out with the same quantities of the reagents to detect copper contamination in any of them.